

Agricultural Podcasting and the Evolution of Agropreneurship in Nigeria: Confluence or Conflict?

Nworie, Chukwuebuka Stephen

chukwuebuka.nworie@ebsu.edu.ng

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3825-9070>

Department of Mass Communication, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki

Abstract

Objective: This work aimed to ascertain how agricultural podcasts have evolved (or declined) agropreneurship in Nigeria.

Method: A descriptive survey was utilized to gather the Nigerians' experiences and perspectives on agri-podcasts and the growth and adoption of agropreneurship. A close-ended questionnaire of 22 elements was used to sample 293 Nigerians. Applying purposive and accidental sampling techniques, 293 respondents were reached through selected podcasts (The Agric Business Show, The Farm Africa, Agri Venture NG, AGRA, and the Lasgidi Farmer Podcast). Data were presented in a percentage frequency table, and the weighted mean table of a 4-point Likert scale was shown.

Result: A high level of knowledge and awareness of agropreneurship among Nigerians exists courtesy of agri-podcasts. Again, agricultural podcasts existed in the evolution of agropreneurship in Nigeria and the uptake of agropreneurship/agro-business or agro-allied ventures as viable sources of employment and incomes by Nigerians. However, a reported conflict exists between agricultural practices as projected by agri-podcasts and the traditional farming system in Nigeria.

Conclusion: Government and extension agents should use podcasts and other new media technologies/platforms to educate the people and campaign for the country's agricultural development in collaboration with traditional institutions and practices.

Keywords: Agricultural podcast; evolution; agropreneurship, conflict; traditional farming system

Introduction

Digital information technologies have revolutionized all sectors of human endeavour. The determinism school of thought has been vindicated by the unwavering power and place of information and communication technologies in modern society. With new possibilities offered by information and communications technology (ICT), Spielman et al. (2021) argued that an abundance of products, services, and projects has emerged with the promise of revitalizing agricultural extension in developing countries. However, evidence suggests that not all ICT-enabled extension approaches are equally effective in improving adoption, productivity, income, or welfare outcomes. To a great extent, ICTs have enabled agricultural extension and invariably ensured food security across the globe (Cui et al., 2018; Chiver et al., 2023). Social innovation has emerged as a possible sustainable solution to economic, educational and societal challenges, argued Binuyo et al. (2020), and includes the problems of poor development of the agricultural sector and agribusiness, high rate of graduates' unemployment, among others. Among the modern technologies and platforms for propagating agricultural issues is podcasting. Ayim et al. (2022), citing the World Bank (2021), submitted that close to 70% of Africans depend on agriculture for their livelihood. This makes agriculture a critical sector within the African continent. Nonetheless, agricultural productivity in the continent is below the global food security expectations, and food insecurity is still challenging. In recent years, this has led to several initiatives to use ICT to improve agricultural productivity. Podcasting is one of the most viable platforms for encouraging participation, demonstration, interactivity, and global reach.

Podcasting is a neo-syllogism of iPod and broadcasting. It is the use of a digital platform to broadcast messages with participatory features that are not available in conventional broadcasting. It incorporates interactivity, modern storage and retrieval features, global reach and availability, limited censorship and control, and an increased use of user-centred design approaches. (Steinke et al., 2021).

Podcasting is the media convergence of broadcasting and internet communication. Although from the inception, podcasting is only on iPod, today, podcasting has evolved to be present in most internet-connected gadgets be it iPod, Android, Apple, MacBook, etc. as reported by Joseph (2025), there is greater accessibility and flexibility of the mobile and open online courses like podcasts and their like which could be used to express a need for more interactive exercises to develop practical pitching skills better, and can effectively support specific skill-building in agropreneurship by incorporating hands-on elements to enhance real-world application of agricultural practices.

The integral relationship between information/communication and the development of agriculture is overwhelming. Furthermore, why we argue the negating cases of poor information and communication gaps in agricultural issues, a glance at the uptake of agriculture as a means of employment (agropreneurship) is heralded on the level of awareness and communicated motivations available to the general public. As captured by Dharmawan (2020), poor agricultural information creates a gap between extensionists and farmers, thereby dwindling agricultural innovations, entrepreneurship opportunities and food security. Podcasting on agricultural issues is a digital agricultural extension. This wider gap in the conventional media is now closed by the decentralized internet-based communication. Schroeder, Lampietti, and Elabed (2021) submitted that the World Bank reveals the paramount role of digital transformation in attaining the SDGs on agriculture by supporting agriculturists to adopt new policies worldwide. Good digital agricultural extension propels people to adopt agriculture as a means of livelihood. This new dimension to economic survival and sustainability is called agropreneurship (Hurley et al., 2020; Vigani et al., 2020).

One of the major causes of food insecurity is the decrease in the number of people who take agriculture as full-time engagement and means of employment. Prequel to that, there has been recorded decline in this engagement among the people, especially in Sub-Sahara Africa. “Even though 80 per cent of the land in Nigeria is arable, less than half of this land is currently cultivated for use and agricultural sector has the capacity to employ over 70 per cent of the entire Nigeria population which implies that there are lots of unexplored opportunities in the sector” (Adeyanju, Mburu, & Mignouna, 2019; Asikhia, 2020). This decline has led to food insecurity and other negating socio-economic issues. However, the advent of digital propagation of agriculture issue through podcasting has gone far in either closing the gap thereof or widening it. Taye (2013) in Steinke, et al. (2021, 549) submitted that “Interest in improving agricultural extension by digital media is high because established methods, such as Training and Visit or Farmer Field Schools, have not always achieved desired outcomes in terms of technology adoption or livelihood improvements.” Contrary to these views, Nwabueze (2024) argued that community-based media channels are more efficient in agricultural extension media campaigns.

“Given future demands for foodstuffs needed to sustain a global populace exceeding nine billion”, argued Jordan et al. (2025, 1), “educators are tasked with promoting understanding of international agricultural issues.” Educators with such a task also demand the utilization of favourable media and platforms for promoting and uptake agriculture as a means of sustainable employment. To this end, this work tends to:

1. Evaluate the extent to which agricultural podcasts have increased awareness and knowledge about agropreneurship among Nigerians
2. Analyse how agricultural podcasts contribute to developing entrepreneurial skills among aspiring and existing agropreneurs in Nigeria.
3. Determine whether agricultural podcasts have influenced Nigerians' adoption of agropreneurship as a viable employment option.
4. Explore whether the content of agricultural podcasts aligns with or conflicts with traditional farming practices in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Diffusion of innovation theory by Everett Rogers was adopted as the theoretical framework of this research. The technological introduction and acceptance theory was developed by Rogers in 1962 to explain how innovations spread across societies and how different people accept or reject such innovations. According to Ansemah et al. (2017), the earliest form of diffusion of innovation was introducing and adopting agricultural equipment and practices. This theory encompasses how and why, over time, an idea or product such as agropreneurship through agricultural podcasting gains/losses momentum and diffuses or becomes extinct through a specific population. Adoption, therefore, indicates how and at what rate these innovations of ideas or products are accepted/rejected, used and reused in society.

Another proposition of this theory is that members of the society must not enjoy similar awareness, acceptance and use of new ideas or products, such as exposure to agropreneurship podcasts. Moreover, people do not have equal access owing to economic and social factors; people do enjoy equal acceptance; owing to psycho-physiological issues; people do not accept the idea or product owing to ideological inclinations, access to the information/communication channels, etc (Wogu, 2023). The proponent identified these cases as innovation, communication channels, time, and social system. These peculiarities lead to innovators, early adopters, later adopters and the laggards.

In consonance to this work, we avail that agropreneurship podcasting as an innovation could have faced similar issues in its diffusion among Nigerians ranging to varying rates of acceptance, rejection, time and rate of acceptance, variance in use/application which are dependent on when and how they are exposed to the podcasts, the socio-economic factors around them, their ideologies. In summary, agropreneurship could be confluent or conflicted with these factors that determine the diffusion of agropreneurship through podcasting. To this end, we therefore hypothesized, in an alternate form, that:

1. Agricultural podcasts have significantly increased the awareness and knowledge about agropreneurship among Nigerians
2. Agricultural podcasts have contributed significantly to developing entrepreneurial skills among aspiring and existing agropreneurs in Nigeria.
3. Agricultural podcasts have influenced Nigerians' adoption of agropreneurship as a viable employment option.
4. The contents of modern agricultural podcasts align with the traditional farming practices in Nigeria.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was employed. The survey was considered fit enough to measure the perspectives of Nigerians on agricultural podcasting and their adoption of agropreneurship as an employment option. The 251 million Nigerians formed the population. 293 respondents (76% of the sample) were randomly studied using a structured online survey questionnaire instrument. The

respondents were reached using the comment session of some selected social media podcast platforms- The Agric Business Show, The Farm Africa, Agri Venture NG, AGRA, and the Lasgidi Farmer Podcast. The selection was purposively done to ensure that only podcasts focusing on agriculture and agropreneurship were used. Data were presented in frequency distribution tables and a weighted mean table. Hypotheses were tested using a weighted mean table under a 4-point Likert format with a 2.50 midpoint.

Data Presentation

The questionnaire instrument was divided in two sections. Section one was used to elucidate demographic features of the respondents. Section two was structured in 4-point Likert scale to measure the respondents' perspectives on the subject matter.

Table 1: Demographic data of the respondents

Questions	Frequency	%
Geopolitical zone of origin:		
South-South	56	19.1
North-Central	16	5.4
South-West	89	30.3
South-East	94	32.0
North-East	18	6.1
North-West	30	10.2
Gender:		
Male	184	62.8
Female	109	37.2
Age:		
15-25	92	31.4
26-35	108	36.9
36-45	66	22.5
46-above	27	9.2
Income per annum (#):		
Less than 100,000	1	0.3
100,000-500,000	194	66.2
500,000-1,000,000	23	7.8
More than 1,000,000	75	25.6
Occupation (multiple choice):		
Unemployed	21	7.2
Agribusinesses/agriculture	104	35.5
Civil service	85	29.0
Non-agro businesses	152	51.9
others	117	39.9

Cut across gender and age, most of the respondents who were considered active participants to agricultural podcasting are mainly southerners. More than 71% earn less than \$1000 yearly. That is less than 100 monthly and not up to 4 daily. This indicates high poverty index in Nigeria. Only a few respondents indicated they are agropreneurs.

Table 2: Evaluation of how agricultural podcasts have increased awareness and knowledge about agropreneurship among Nigerians

Questions	Responses analysis					Decision
	SA	A	D	SD	X ²	
1. Agricultural podcasts provide new information about agropreneurship among Nigerians	53	121	47	72	2.52	Accept
2. Agricultural podcasts have improved my understanding of the steps required to start and sustain agri-businesses	39	61	104	89	2.17	Reject
3. I am more aware of agricultural issues like agri-networks, agri/agro-allied funding, mentorships/extension programmes, etc., because of my exposure/participation in agri-podcasts.	82	71	94	46	2.64	Accept
4. Agri-podcasts have taught me new and innovative farming techniques that can increase my agri-businesses	109	85	62	37	2.91	Accept
5. I have an increased interest in agropreneurship due to my exposure/participation to agricultural podcasts	83	64	86	60	2.58	Accept
Total					2.564	Accept

The alternate hypothesis was accepted by applying the weighted mean calculation since the mean value exceeds the 2.50 midpoint mean value. Thus, agricultural podcasts have increased awareness and knowledge about agropreneurship among Nigerians.

Table 3: Assessing how agricultural podcasts contribute to developing entrepreneurial skills among aspiring and existing agropreneurs in Nigeria.

Questions	Response analysis					Decision
	SA	A	D	SD	X ²	
1. Agriculture podcasts have improved my ability to identify viable agribusiness opportunities	95	71	38	89	2.59	Accept
2. I have learnt practical business planning skills from agricultural podcasts	82	57	99	55	2.57	Accept
3. Agri-podcasts have enhanced my understanding of risk management strategies in agribusiness	29	70	112	82	2.16	Reject
4. Agricultural podcasts have built my confidence in agro-allied/ agribusiness funding and investment.	46	95	93	59	2.44	Reject
5. I learnt effective marketing and branding of my agri-businesses through agri-podcasts	66	101	12	114	2.41	Reject
6. I apply innovative farming or agribusiness management techniques learned from agricultural podcasts	89	76	51	77	2.60	Accept
7. Agriculture podcasts have contributed to my overall agropreneurship growth	116	52	44	81	2.69	Accept
Total					2.50	Accept

The midpoint value and the calculated weighted mean value are equal. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis should be accepted. Thus, agricultural podcasts contribute to developing entrepreneurial skills among aspiring and existing agropreneurs in Nigeria.

Table 4: Ascertaining the influences of agricultural podcasts on the adoption of agropreneurship as a viable employment option by Nigerians

Question	Response Analysis					Decision
	SA	A	D	SD	X2	
1. I am motivated to pursue agropreneurship as a source of income after learning about success stories on agri-podcasts.	118	65	35	75	2.77	Accept
2. Agri-podcasts made me view agropreneurship as a realistic and sustainable career choice	104	79	48	62	2.77	Accept
3. I am currently an agropreneur due to my exposure to agri-podcasts	54	105	63	71	2.48	Reject
4. I will align with and accept agropreneurship compared to traditional employment options	88	92	29	84	2.63	Accept
5. I am currently equipped with my exposure to agri-podcasts on the practical knowledge to transition agropreneurship as primary and secondary income	102	63	47	71	2.60	Accept
Total					2.65	Accept

From the calculation in Table 4 above, we deduce that agri-podcasts have significantly improved agropreneurship in Nigeria by projecting it as a viable source of income to the citizenry.

Table 5: Ascertaining the conflicts/confluence between agricultural podcasts and traditional farming practices in Nigeria

Questions	Response Analysis					Decision
	SA	A	D	SD	X2	
1. Agri-podcasts promote farming techniques that are compatible with traditional Nigerian agricultural practices	53	42	116	82	2.22	Reject
2. Agri-podcasts emphasize solutions that complement traditional farming practices	41	55	89	108	2.09	Reject
3. Agri-podcasts respect and integrate cultural values associated with Nigerian farming traditions	47	39	125	82	2.17	Reject
4. Agri-podcasts often dismiss traditional farming practices as outdated and inefficient	108	92	52	41	2.91	Accept

5. The technologies and innovations in agri-podcasts conflict with the tools/modules of traditional farming practices in Nigeria	88	107	50	48	2.80	Accept
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As revealed by the above table, modern agri-podcasts conflict with traditional agricultural practices in Nigeria. Hence, we presume that new innovations in agriculture and agropreneurship are revolutionary to traditional farming systems in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Summarily, this survey found that agricultural podcasts have increased the level of awareness and knowledge about agropreneurship among Nigerians, contributed to the development of entrepreneurial skills among aspiring and existing agropreneurs in Nigeria, and significantly helped improve agropreneurship in Nigeria by projecting it as a viable source of income to the citizenry. However, the agricultural practices propagated in the agri-podcasts conflict with Nigeria's traditional agricultural /farming practices.

The increment of awareness of agropreneurship among Nigerians through agri-podcasts is a pointer to the convergence role of modern technologies in agricultural development in Nigeria. Considering the unemployment rate and economic conditions, the utility of new media and the blending of broadcasting to educate the public about entrepreneurship in agriculture is a significant social responsibility role of the press in national development. In a similar case, Coggins et al. (2022) argue that the digital extension tools (DETs) have garnered significant coverage of agricultural issues, and their impact is enormous on the world's agricultural development. Although exposure, knowledge, adoption, and acceptance of these DETs are unequal among countries of the world, Nigerians have recorded high knowledge of agropreneurship among agriculture issues through podcasts.

Secondly, the survey indicated significant contributions of agricultural podcasts to developing agropreneurship in Nigeria. The advent of new media and information technologies has invariably propelled the growth of many sectors and created opportunities for their integral functioning. Agropreneurship is a response to the food insecurity and unemployment that have plagued Nigeria and most countries worldwide. The readiness of extension agents to use DETs would enhance agricultural development and create employment opportunities (Dharmawan et al., 2020).

Contrary to the submission made by Emeh et al. (2023), Nigerians are increasingly moving into agriculture. Although there still exists a significant unemployment rate, a low percentage of uptake of agropreneurship, and a lack of employment, most Nigerians have entrepreneurship as a source of income rather than white-collar jobs. There should be a continuous media campaign on agropreneurship to tackle this. The percentage of agropreneurs in Nigeria is greater than we had years ago. The Youth Service Skill Acquisition and Entrepreneurship Development (SAED) has done marvelously well in this angle.

Although this survey showed a positive role and impact of agricultural podcasts on the awareness, knowledge and development of agropreneurship in Nigeria, significant discrepancies exist between the extension information in the podcasts and the traditional farming system in Nigeria. This could cause a setback in the adoption of agropreneurship in Nigeria. Agriculture in some clans in sub-Saharan Africa is culturally bound. Conflicting extension information in DETs can thwart the agricultural programmes and reduce the adoption rate of agropreneurship practices among the people.

Conclusion

The digitalization of agricultural extension and development campaigns will create a better avenue for the growth and agropreneurship in Nigeria. While there is an argument on the state of unemployment and food security in Nigeria, one cannot write off the development of agropreneurship, which is significantly tied to the advent of DETs. In the 1900s and even early 2000s, the laggardness in agropreneurship was higher compared to the 2020s. However, the media still have much to do in reshaping the basic factors (culture, finance, government policies and laws, etc.) that could mar or make a soft ground for the thriving career uptake in agriculture and agribusinesses in Nigeria.

Recommendations

To guide policies, programmes, and institutions pertinent to the attainment of the aforementioned research objectives, the following recommendations should be adhered to:

1. Government and private extension agents should adopt podcasting to increase awareness and knowledge of agricultural practices and programmes. This would enable the public to make informed decisions and take action to grow agropreneurship in Nigeria.
2. To ensure a greater role of agri-podcasts on the evolution of agropreneurship in Nigeria, extension agents and government institutions should include demonstrative and practical agricultural techniques to enable the public to have experiential knowledge that could propel positive action. Testimonials, support, collaborations, and assistance in agro-businesses/agro-allied are ways to ensure the growth of agropreneurship in Nigeria.
3. Collaboration with traditional institutions and farmers will help advocate for change in the system and reduce the conflict between the modern and traditional farming systems. This will invariably assist in curtailing the rate of antagonism played by the conflicting factors.

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